

2016 Usage Report for the IPCC DDC

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2017-03-17	0.1	Initial report presented to TGICA showing evidence of unusual reporting from Google Analytics in late 2016.
2017-03-21	1.0	Update to the initial report with unusual reporting filtered out of the DDC usage analysis.

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1. Summary

This report provides details of how the DDC web site, ipcc-data.org, was used in the 12 months from January 1st 2016 to December 31st 2016. The information presented here is generated using the Google Analytics service; providing a range of different statistics that cover both temporal and spatial trends. Only sessions which persist for longer than 10 seconds have been used in this analysis for consistency with the previous usage reports for TGICA. The Google Analytics statistics have also been filtered to remove robotic and other automated behaviour. 2016 was chosen as the reporting period for DDC usage statistics rather than the 12 months prior to the writing of this report to facilitate comparison with the download statistics reported by the DKRZ.

DDC access statistics for 2016 show a fall of about 9% compared to 2015. The Home page remains the most commonly viewed page on the DDC.

2. Evolution of User Sessions

The number of DDC page views recorded in 2016 is lower than the number of page views received in the previous year, a fall of about 9% from 199273 views in 2015 to 182180 views in 2016. Nevertheless the DDC continues to regularly receive over 2500 page views per week. A clear feature of both the 2015 and 2016 time series is a drop-off in session numbers during the Christmas holiday season (week index 0, 51 and 52). 2016 can be characterised by the reduction in page views in the period from September-December when compared to the same period in previous years.

Weekly user sessions (longer than 10s) for the last five years are shown in figure 2 and provide a context for the two years of page view statistics shown in figure 1.

Figure1: Time series of weekly DDC page views for sessions with duration longer than 10s. The time axis is shown in weeks from December 28th of the previous year. Two time series are shown: red for the period from December 27th 2015 to December 31st 2016 and blue for the previous 12 months from December 28th 2014 to January 2nd 2016.

Figure 2: Weekly user sessions (longer than 10s) for the five years from January 2012 to December 2016 inclusive.

3. Access Patterns by Page on the DDC

The IPCC-DDC home page remains the most commonly viewed page on the DDC, receiving 11% of page views in 2016 (figure 3). Other popular pages are those that explain some of the basic science behind climate change such as: Projected emissions and concentrations of carbon dioxide; Understanding the observational record; An Introduction to Global Climate Models (GCMs). It is clear that users are interested in using the DDC to access GCM data and information about the IPCC 5th Assessment Report (AR5).

The access pattern of pages across the IPCC-DDC is very similar to the distribution recorded in the July 2016 usage report. The only significant change is a renewed interest in the regional scatterplots which have moved up from 47th place to be the 10th most popular page.

Most users arriving at the DDC do so via the Home page, just as previously reported to TGICA in September 2015 and July 2016. It is helpful to know that users tend to arrive on the home page because this is where we provide information about the purpose of the site and an overview of the content that we provide. Most users visiting the guidance pages navigate there from another page on the DDC, this fits with the behaviour of a person who, having found some interesting data, decides to use our guidance documents to learn how to use it.

Again it is worth reiterating the importance of popular entry pages such as “What is a GCM?” and “CO2” as places where additional contextual information about the DDC can be placed. This is especially important to keep in mind if we move to a more modular site design in the future.

Figure 3: Access distribution across the various pages of the IPCC-DDC that were visited during 2016.

Page on the DDC	URL	Number of unique Views	%
Home	www.ipcc-data.org/index.html	13533	11.42
Observations	www.ipcc-data.org/observ/index.html	7681	6.48
AR5 GCM data	www.ipcc-data.org/sim/gcm_monthly/AR5/index.html	6036	5.09
CO2	www.ipcc-data.org/observ/ddc_co2.html	5864	4.95
Simulations	www.ipcc-data.org/sim/index.html	5462	4.61
Climate Model Output	www.ipcc-data.org/sim/gcm_monthly/index.html	4317	3.64
What is a GCM?	www.ipcc-data.org/guidelines/pages/gcm_guide.html	3577	3.02
AR4 GCM data	www.ipcc-data.org/sim/gcm_monthly/SRES_AR4/index.html	3206	2.71
Guidance	www.ipcc-data.org/guidelines/index.html	3021	2.55
Regional Scatterplots	www.ipcc-data.org/syn/tar_scatter/index.html	2906	2.45
Scenario Process for AR5: RCPs	sedac.ipcc-data.org/ddc/ar5_scenario_process/RCPs.html	2874	2.42
AR5 Reference Snapshot	www.ipcc-data.org/sim/gcm_monthly/AR5/Reference-Archive.html	2658	2.24
Scenario Process for AR5	sedac.ipcc-data.org/ddc/ar5_scenario_process/index.html	2579	2.18
AR4 Observations	www.ipcc-data.org/observ/clim/ar4_global.html	2256	1.90
CRU_TS 2.1	www.ipcc-data.org/observ/clim/cru_ts2_1.html	1815	1.53

Table 1: The same information as in the pie chart in figure 3 but with the page URLs shown.

Figure 4: The overall number of unique views per page (blue) and the number of entrances per page (red) during 2016. Users tend to arrive at pages where the number of entrances are about equal to the number of page views and navigate to pages where the number of entrances are much less than the number of page views.

4. Geographical Distribution of Engagement with the DDC

Figure 5: The geographical distribution of DDC sessions (duration > 10s) by continent for 2016

Figure 6: The geographical distribution of DDC user sessions (duration > 10s) by country for 2016.

Sessions initiated by users in Europe, Asia and North America account for 85% of DDC activity (figure 5) however approximately half of the DDC sessions are initiated by users in just six countries. Nevertheless the DDC plays an increasingly important role in many countries in spite of their relatively small number of page views.

Figure 6, which names the top 17 countries that make use of the DDC, is a useful way to showcase those countries that access the DDC most frequently. Users in the top 6 countries account for 49% of all sessions: USA 21%, UK 8%, China 6%, India 6%, Iran 4% and Germany 4%. “other” countries not listed here account for 28% of user sessions.

4.1 DDC Engagement from Africa

There are no countries from Africa listed in the pie chart shown in figure 6 yet DDC engagement from African users has seen a dramatic increase in recent years and African users account for 5% of DDC sessions in 2016.

The evolution of African engagement from 2009-2016 is illustrated in figures 7 and 8 which show a rapid 188% increase in user sessions from 2011 to 2015, that contrasts with only a 72% increase in usage from the rest of the world over the same period. The period from 2011-2015 has also witnessed the additional participation of a further 14 countries from across the continent. In 2016 the greatest engagement with the DDC across Africa came from users based in South Africa, Ethiopia, Kenya, Egypt and Nigeria.

Figure 7: Annual DDC user sessions (duration > 10s) for Africa and all other continents.

Figure 8: Geographical distribution of DDC user sessions (duration > 10s) in Africa. Map shading is relative to the number of sessions in the most active country.

5. Browser Statistics

The IPCC-DDC site is available and accessible to all the major internet browsers and operating systems (figure 9). Chrome is the most popular browser, accounting for 60% of sessions; Windows is the most popular operating system, accounting for 78% of sessions; English is the most used language setting, accounting for 69% of sessions.

Figure 9: Browser and technology characteristics of DDC user sessions with information about Browsers, Operating Systems and Language settings.